

Comparative Study on Proximate Composition of Fruit Pulp of African Locust Bean (*Parkia biglobosa* L.) Collected from two Different Markets in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The research was carried out to determine the proximate contents of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp collected from Dankure and Marna Market, Sokoto. Standard Analytical Method of Association of Analytical Chemists (AOAC) was used. The result on proximate analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp obtained from Dankure Market, Sokoto showed that, the carbohydrate contents of fruit pulp had the highest value of 73.00 ± 8.14 , followed by Moisture content with 15.50 ± 1.22 and the least was Fiber with 2.17 ± 0.84 while that of Marna Market showed that, Carbohydrates had the highest value of 71.34 ± 0.00 , followed by Moisture contents with 14.26 ± 0.29 and the least was Fiber with 2.21 ± 0.05 . In conclusion, the Carbohydrate, moisture and Protein content in Dankure Market is higher than that of Marna Market while the Protein content and Fiber content were higher in Marna Market than in Dankure Market. This research recommended the use of fruit pulp of *Parkia biglobosa* as a good source of energy due to the presences of high content of Carbohydrates, protein and moisture in both the two market.

Keywords: Dankure, Market, Marna, Nigeria *Parkia biglobosa*, Sokoto.

1.0 Introduction

Parkia biglobosa tree is a deciduous tree with a very broad crown that may reach a height of 20m. The species grows under a wide range of conditions, where annual rainfall ranges from 600 to 1500 mm and the dry season last 5-7 month [1]. It occurs in natural and semi-natural habitats such as savannahs and woodlands, sometimes on rocky slopes, stony ridges and sandstone hills [2]. It is able to withstand drought because of its deep taproot [1]. Together with the shear butter tree (*Vittelaria paradoxa*), African locust bean is one of the main component agro forestry parkland in west Africa [3]. *Parkia biglobosa* is one of the indigenous medicinal plants commonly found in Nigeria and many African countries. The fermented seeds of *Parkia biglobosa* are believed to possess nutritional and medicinal value; hence, they are often inset in the preparation of various delicious foods [3]. *Parkia biglobosa* belong to the family *Leguminosae* and subfamily *Mimosoideae*. *Parkia biglobosa* is a

dicotyledonous angiosperm belonging to the family *fabaceae*. It is categorized under spermatophytes, vascular plant [3]. It is a deciduous perennial that grows between 7 and 20 meters high [1]. The tree is a fire resistant halophyte characterized by a thick dark grey-brown bark [4]. The pods of the tree, commonly referred to as locust beans, are pink in the beginning and turn dark brown when fully mature [4]. They are 30-40cm long average, with some reaching length of about 45 cm, each pod contain up to 30 seeds. Leaves alternate, bipinnately compound, up to 30-40 cm long, stipules absent, petiole 4-125cm long, swollen at base and there with an orbicular gland, rachis with a caduceus awn at apex bearing up 17 pairs of pinnae, with a gland between the terminal pinnae [1-4].

Parkia biglobosa also known as “Dorowa” in Hausa “African locust bean” In English, “irou” in Yoruba, “Origili” in Igbo have been known to be a native of African savannah land one of the most common species of the parkland agro forestry

system [5]. More attention have been given to economically important species of tree plants especially *Parkia biglobosa* in increasing recognition of its contribution to fulfill basic needs of people, household, food security and conservation of natural resources [6]. The tree of the area where they grow because they are valuable sources of reliable food, wood production, supply of timbers, firewood pulp and fire through fodder, gum, drugs and dyes as well as restoration of fertility [2]. The Nigeria study submitted that leaves, fruits, nuts and oils obtained from *Parkia biglobosa* have provided for human, livestock and wild life in many of the country. The rood, barks, leaves, stem flowers, fruits and seed of *Parkia biglobosa* are all used medicinally to treat a range of ailments including diarrhea, ulcers, pneumonia, burns, coughs and jaundice [2-7].

Hassan et al. [8] reported that *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp has poor essential amino acid content with a score of 1/8. The pulp contains higher cellulose and less ascorbic acid than the cotyledons. The pulp also contains simple sugars accept maltose [4]. The seeds of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp on fermentation are used in cooking stew and soup, the sweet yellow pulp contains 60% sugar when ripe and the seeds contain 30% protein as well as vitamin and minerals [9-7]. The fruits pods are used to produce insecticide powders for treating crops. The fermented seeds of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp are used in all part of Nigeria and indeed the west coast of Africa for seasoning traditional soup [10].

The nutritional composition and proximate analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp have been of interest due to its traditional uses and potential

as a food source. However, there is a lack of comprehensive and up-to-date information on the proximate composition, including moisture content, ash content, lipid content, protein content, and carbohydrate content [11]. Additionally, variations in the proximate composition based on geographical locations and ripening stages have not been thoroughly explored [12]. This research aims to address these gaps and provide a detailed proximate analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp to enhance our understanding of its nutritional value and potential applications in the food industry."

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Sokoto metropolis at in Sokoto state, Nigeria. Sokoto is a city located in the extreme northwest of Nigeria, near the confluence of the Sokoto River and the Rima River. It occupies 25,973 square kilometers with a population of 563,861. Geographically situated between 13.0609° N latitude and 5.2431° E longitude east with an average elevation of 272m above sea level [13]. The wet season lasts from June to September. Annual rainfall ranges between 300mm and 800mm while mean annual temperature is 34°C with dry seasons temperatures often exceeding 40°C. Sokoto is located in the Sahel region of Nigeria, characterized by a semi-arid climate. The vegetation in this region is influenced by factors such as temperature, precipitation, and soil type [13]. Agriculture is the mainstay of the people. Major dry season vegetable crops which are mainly grown under irrigation include Onion, Tomato, Sweet and Hot pepper others include Carrot, Rice, Wheat and garden egg [10]

Figure 1: Map of Marna Market, Sokoto,

Figure 2: Map of Dankure Market, Sokoto.

2.2 Sample Collection and Preparation

Parkia biglobosa fruit pulp was obtained from Marina and Dankure Market, Sokoto. The samples were packaged in a sterile polythene bag, and transported to the Chemistry laboratory of Sokoto State University, Sokoto.

2.3 Proximate Analysis of Sample

Comparative proximate analysis of moisture content, ash content, crude protein, crude fiber, and lipid content on *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp samples were determined according to standard method of Association of Official Chemist [14]. While Carbohydrate content was estimated using the modified at water factors [14].

2.3.1 Determination of moisture content

The principle of moisture content determination was based on heating the sample of eliminates all the water content in the sample in an oven at 105°C. Two gram of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp was measured in an empty petri dish which has been cleaned and dried in an oven at 80°C for about 30minutes. The empty moisture can was weighed (W_0), 2grams of the sample was added and weigh the moisture again with the sample (W_1).The sample in the can was dried in an oven at 105°C. The can was removed from the oven and cooled in a desiccators for 20minutes. The can with dry sample was weigh, and it was measured (W_2).The dried sample was returned in the oven to make sure the drying is complete. It was weighed again; the weight (W_2) should be constant now otherwise it will be dried again in the oven until constant weight is obtained. The difference in the weight after heating gives the moisture content is determine by subtracting the dry weight the dry wet weight.

Calculation

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1 - W_0} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: W_0 = weight of container
 W_1 = weight of container and sample before drying; and
 W_2 = weight of container and sample after drying.

2.3.2 Determination of Ash content

The principle is based on the fact that minerals are not destroyed by high temperature. When a food material is ash in a muffle furnace at high temperature of 600°C for all the organic matter is

burnt off leaving the in organic substance in the form of Ash. The crucible was weigh, (W_0). The sample was added in a crucible and was weighed (W_1). Ash in the muffle furnace at 600°C, cool the sample in a desiccators and weigh the crucible and Ash sample (W_2).

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_2} \times 100 \quad \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where: W_0 = weight of crucible
 W_1 = weight of crucible and sample; and
 W_2 = weight of crucible and ash sample.

2.3.3 Determination of Crude Protein by Regular Macro-kjeldahl Method

The principle for the determination of protein content is based on fact that when a sample is boiled with concentrated sulphuric acid, it decomposes the organic substance by oxidation and converts all forms of nitrogen to the reduced form of ammonium sulphate. The distillation of the solution with excess sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in closed system neutralizes the acid and converts ammonium. The amount of ammonia present in the sample is determined by distilling the ammonia into boric acid solution (H_2BO_3) and titrates against 0,1N HCC to end point. Equation of reaction involves 3 steps:

i. Digestion

ii. Distillation

a. Liberation of Ammonia

b. Capture of ammonia

The procedure was conducted in three steps analysis which includes digestion, distillation and titration

Digestion

Exactly 0.5 gram of the sample was weighed in to a dry 500ml macro-kjeldahl flask and 20ml of distilled water was added. The flask was swirled for few minutes and was allowed to stand for 30minutes. A tablet of Selenium was added, and 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 was added through an automatic pipette. The flask was heated carefully at low heat on the digestion stand. When the water has been dissolved or frothing ceased, the heat will be increased until the digest clears.

And then the mixture was boiled for 5 hours. Regulate the heating during this boiling so that the H_2SO_4 condenses about middle of the neck of the flask. The flask was allowed to cool and about 50 ml of water was added slowly to the flask. 10 ml of the digest was carefully transferred into clean macro-kjeldahl distilled water and then the aliquots was transferred into the same flask.

Distillation

About 20 ml of boric acid solution was added into 250 ml flask, which was then placed under the condenser of the distillation apparatus. The end of the condenser was 4 cm above the surface of the Boric acid solution. 750 ml kjeldahl flask was attached to the distillation apparatus, and about 20 ml of 40% NaOH was added through distillation flask by opening the funnel stopcock. The distillation was started immediately. The condenser was kept cool (below $30^{\circ}C$) by allowing sufficient cold water to through, and the heat was regulated to minimize frothing and prevent suck-back. 40 ml of the distillate was collected and then the distillation was stopped.

Titration

The collected distillate was cooled and titrated against 0.1 M hydrochloric acid to an end point which is indicated by change of colour from green to pink.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen} = \frac{T_v \times N \times 0.014 \times 50 \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times \text{ml (s) of Aliquo}} \dots (3)$$

Where

N = Normality (0.1)

2.3.4 Determination of crude fiber

One gram (1g) of the sample was hydrolyzed in a beaker with petroleum ether after which it was refluxed for 30 minutes with 200 ml of a solution 1.25% H_2SO_4 per 100 ml of solution (W_1). The solution was filtered through filter paper. After filtration, the sample was washed in the boiled water until the sample was no longer acidic. The residue was transferred through filter crucible and dried at $100^{\circ}C$ for 2 hours. This weight (W_2) represents the crude fiber plus ash content in comparison to initial weight.

The percentage crude fibre was thus calculated from the weight after drying and the weight of the sample.

$$\% \text{ Crude fiber} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100 \dots (4)$$

Where: W_1 = weight of the sample

W_2 = weight of the dried sample

2.3.5 Determination of lipid/fat

Two grams (2g) of dried sample was weighed and transferred into a thimble which has been dried and weighed. The thimble containing the sample was weighed (W_2) and the mouth porous thimble was covered with fat free absorbent cotton wool in order to distribute the draping petroleum ether.

The thimble was then placed in a soxhlet extractor fitted to a round bottom flask containing 150 cm of petroleum ether. The apparatus was switched on for 5-6 hours at $50^{\circ}C$. After this, the thimble was removed from the soxhlet and weighed. The flask was removed with care and the organic solvent was evaporated. Finally the extracted flask containing the oil was weighed, in order to know the content of the crude lipid.

Calculation

The percentage of crude lipid is calculated using the equation:

$$\% \text{ crude lipid} = \frac{\text{weight of loss by thimble}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{ crude lipid} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_3} \times 100 \dots (5)$$

Where: W_1 = weight of the empty thimble

W_2 = weight of the flask

W_3 = weight of the sample

2.3.6 Determination of Total Carbohydrate

The total Carbohydrate was determined by subtracting the total percentages of crude protein, crude lipid, moisture content and ash from 100%.

Calculation

$$\% \text{ total carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{ crude protein} + \% \text{ crude lipid} + \% \text{ ash} + \% \text{ moisture}) \dots (6)$$

2.4 Statistical Analysis

The data obtained was subjected to inferential analysis using independent T-Test. The differences between the mean values were evaluated using the Tukey test at the significance level of $P < 0.05$. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed using the package available in R Studio, version 1.1.463.

3.0 Results

Table 1: Proximate Analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* Fruit Pulp obtained from Dankure and Marna Market, Sokoto

Parameters	Compositions	
	Dankure Market	Marna Market
Moisture	15.50±1.22 ^a	14.26± 0.29 ^b
Ash	3.00±0.71 ^a	3.00±0.01 ^b
Lipid	5.57±0.89 ^b	5.69±0.00 ^a
Fiber	2.17±0.84 ^b	2.21±0.05 ^a
Protein	4.00±0.41 ^a	3.50±0.05 ^b
Carbohydrate	73.00±8.13 ^a	71.34±0.00 ^a

Values are means ± standard deviation. Data from rows followed by different letters are significantly different ($p < 0.05$)

The result of proximate analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp obtained from Dankure Market, Sokoto showed that, the carbohydrate contents of fruit pulp had the highest value of 73.00±8.14%, followed by the Moisture content with 15.50±1.22% and the least was Fiber with 2.17±0.84% while that of Marna Market, Sokoto showed that, carbohydrates had the highest value of 71.34±0.00%, followed by the Moisture contents 14.26± 0.29% and the least was Fiber with 2.21±0.05% (Table 1).

4.0 Discussion

The research on comparative study of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp aimed at exploring and analyzing the proximate contents of the fruit pulp in comparison to other relevant counterparts. *Parkia biglobosa*, commonly known as African locust bean, is a tropical tree whose fruit is widely utilized in traditional medicine and culinary practices in various regions [3-5]. This comparative study seeks to shed light on the unique attributes of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp, potentially uncovering its nutritional richness and potential health benefits [5].

The moisture content 15.50±1.22% of fruit pulp of *Parkia biglobosa* from Dankure Market was significantly higher than that of Marna Market with 14.26± 0.29%. There was a significant difference between the moisture content of the

sample from Dankure and Marna Market. The moisture content values reported in this study were lower than the values (23.54%) reported by Yehouenou et al. [15]. However, they were similar to those reported by Zango et al. [16] with a value of (14.20±0.22%) for the samples from Tchad. High moisture content increases the biochemical reactions. A variety of factors affect the moisture, content of food and usually the period and methods of harvesting contributes enormously to the moisture content [17].

The ash composition of *Parkia biglobosa* from Dankure 3.00±0.71% and Marna Market 3.00±0.01% were significantly equal. However, it was observed to be low when compared to the result obtained from the fruit of *Coccosia esculento* 4.23±0.07% by Richard et al. [18]. This observation is in agreement with the reports of Zukachukwu and Obioha [19] who attributed it to the dehulling effect of boiling treatment which may have predisposed the fruit to some kind of leaching of some of its mineral elements. The Ash content gives an idea of the inorganic content of the sample from where the mineral content could be obtained [3]. However, according to Omafuvbe et al. [20], the higher ash value of the fruit pulp seeds may be as a result of loss of moisture due to the application of dry heat, which concentrates the inorganic content which explains the results obtained in this study.

The lipid content 5.57±0.89% of fruit pulp obtained from Dankure Market was significantly different from the value obtained from Marna, Market 5.69±0.00%. The result is in conformity with the result obtained by Richard et al. [18] with value of 5.50±0.77%. This showed that the fruits of *Parkia biglobosa* could be used as a good source of energy.

The crude fibre composition of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit pulp obtained from Dankure Market 2.17±0.84 was significantly lower than the value obtained from Marna Market with (2.21±0.05). The observed low crude fibre is in correlation with the work done by Hassan et al. [8] which revealed that crude fiber of *Parkia biglobosa* fruit to be 2.20±0.29. Fiber plays a role in the prevention of number of diseases by reducing the level of cholesterol.

The result of protein in *Parkia biglobosa* obtained from Dankure Market 4.00±0.41% was significantly higher than the value obtained from Marna Market with 3.50±0.05% which shows that

Parkia biglobosa has lower protein content which is not in line with the result obtained by Muazu [6] who reported a value of 7.68 ± 0.31 .

Carbohydrates content of the fruit pulp ranged from 73.00 ± 8.13 in Dankure Market to 71.34 ± 0.00 in Marna Market. There was no significant difference between the two samples. These values were similar to those reported by Zango et al. [16] ($73.82 \pm 2.51\%$) on samples from Tchad, and there was no significant difference in the Carbohydrate content of the samples from the three eco-regions

The carbohydrate contents of fruit pulp had the highest value. Richard et al., [18] has reported for the high carbohydrates content in *P. biglobosa* fruits. A high carbohydrate food is desirable while deficiency of carbohydrate causes depletion of body tissues [21].

5.0 Conclusion

The study on Comparative Proximate Analysis of *Parkia biglobosa* fruits pulp indicated significant difference on carbohydrates contents, moisture contents and crude fiber in samples collected in Dankure and Marna Market. The results of the study provides valuable insights into its nutritional diversity, offering a foundation for further research and potential applications in the food industry and beyond. These findings contribute to our understanding of this traditional African resource and its significance for both local communities and broader global contexts.

6.0 Recommendations

1. The fruit pulp of *Parkia biglobosa* showed high content of carbohydrate and should be recommended to the communities who often lack enough supply of nutrients such as fibre, protein, fat and minerals.
2. Health and nutrient projects should be adopted with the theme of promoting African locust bean fruit pulp product for value additional and increased utilization.
3. Physio-chemical properties and genetic studies should be conducted within population and further correlated to the nutritional data to understand the effects of soil types and genetics on nutritional content of African locust bean.

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

9.0 References

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